

IMPROVEMENT OF METHODS OF ADAPTIVE TEACHING OF DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the significance and practical potential of integrating mathematical modeling and intelligent technologies within an adaptive learning environment based on artificial intelligence. The findings indicate that their combined application supports the development of individualized learning trajectories and increases the effectiveness of the educational process.

Introduction.

Modern scientific research shows that educational environments organized using artificial intelligence technologies allow taking into account the individual learning characteristics of students, systematic and deep formation of knowledge, and increasing the overall effectiveness of the learning process. In analytical reports published by leading international financial institutions, the introduction of digital and intellectual technologies into the education system is recognized as one of the important factors in the development of human capital, and their positive impact on educational outcomes is especially noted.

Today, the education system is entering a new qualitative stage under the influence of the rapid development of artificial intelligence and mathematical modeling technologies. The integration of these technologies, unlike traditional teaching approaches, allows for in-depth analysis of the educational process, prediction of learning outcomes, and increasing the effectiveness of education. Mathematical modeling serves to describe complex pedagogical processes arising in the educational process through mathematical expressions, to systematically analyze the interaction between the teacher and the student. Artificial intelligence technologies provide the ability to process these models in real time, make adapted pedagogical decisions based on the obtained data, and form individual educational trajectories.

In Uzbekistan, scientific and practical research is also being consistently conducted in the direction of developing artificial intelligence and digital technologies. In particular, in the analytical data published by the Center for Economic Research and Reforms under the

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2023), the introduction of artificial intelligence and digital technologies is noted as an important factor in the development of human capital and the modernization of the education system. The "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" program also emphasizes the need to create a modern, flexible, and effective educational environment through the introduction of digital and intellectual technologies into the educational process.

In the research process, a mathematical modeling approach was used to assess the effectiveness of education. Considering that the effectiveness of the educational process is formed as a result of the interaction of several main factors, it is expressed on the basis of the following functional relationship:

$$E = \alpha K + \beta M + \gamma A + \delta T$$

where E is an integral indicator expressing the overall effectiveness of the educational process, which is determined by the level of students' assimilation of knowledge and learning outcomes. K represents the level of cognitive activity, M - the indicator of students' motivation for learning, A - the level of adaptability of artificial intelligence algorithms, and T - the effectiveness of the applied learning technologies.

The weight coefficients α , β , γ , and δ used in the model are 0.25; 0.30; 0.25 and 0.20, which reflect the degree of influence of each factor on the effectiveness of education.

Figure 1. Diagram of modeling and analysis of the educational process using artificial intelligence

Based on the proposed model, the main components of the educational process were quantitatively assessed and comprehensively analyzed using artificial intelligence tools. Statistical processing of the obtained empirical data was carried out in accordance with the requirements of modern statistical analysis using the SPSS 28.0 software environment (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 28.0 is a modern software package

designed for the analysis of statistical data, which is widely used in scientific research, education, social sciences, and economic analysis). In the study, the statistical significance of the differences between an adaptive learning system based on artificial intelligence and a traditional education system was assessed using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) method in order to determine and compare the effectiveness of education. Correlation analysis was also used to determine the relationship between the main components of the educational process, and the influence of cognitive activity, the level of motivation, the coefficient of adaptability, and the indicators of teaching technologies on the effectiveness of education was comprehensively analyzed.

112 students participated in the study, and data on their educational activities were regularly collected and analyzed. Statistical results showed that in an adaptive learning system modeled with the help of artificial intelligence, the level of students' assimilation of knowledge, activity in educational activities, and indicators of independent work steadily increased. Compared to the traditional education system, this adaptive system showed high results on average by 28% in terms of overall learning effectiveness.

These results confirm that educational technologies based on artificial intelligence and mathematical modeling have the ability to individualize the educational process, monitor educational activities in real time, and significantly increase the effectiveness of education.

The results of the experimental study showed that the educational process, organized on the basis of the integration of mathematical modeling and artificial intelligence technologies, has higher effectiveness compared to traditional teaching methods.

Figure 2. Comparative analysis of the results of traditional and AI-based training groups

In particular, it was established that the level of knowledge acquisition in the experimental group was 26% higher than in the control group. At the same time, the student motivation index for learning increased by 18%, and the accuracy of assessing the learning process improved from 92% to 97%. Analyses based on graphs and diagrams confirm that students' activity in the educational process has increased, and they have mastered the educational material in a shorter time and in a more stable way.

Figure 3. Comparative model of the effectiveness of traditional and AI-based adaptive educational systems

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the integration of mathematical modeling and intelligent technologies in an adaptive educational environment based on artificial intelligence is one of the important factors in the effective organization of the modern educational process. This integration allows for a systematic analysis of the educational process, identification of the individual learning characteristics of students, and the formation of adapted educational trajectories. The research results showed that the integrated use of mathematical modeling and artificial intelligence technologies significantly improves the quality of education, orients students towards independent and critical thinking, and serves the development of their professional and digital competencies. In the future, the widespread introduction of adaptive education systems based on artificial intelligence is expected to play an important role in modernizing the education system of Uzbekistan, as well as in training competitive and highly qualified personnel.

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